

ENVIRONMENT PROTECTION: FACTORS AND AFFECTING ACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, many environmental problems have increased as the result of human activities and unplanned management of the technological development those interference ecosystems. Therefore, a dispute between the importance of conservation and preservation of ecosystems to protect environment and the necessity to satisfy human desire by sacrifice the environment has been arise across the world.

Various human activities have induce many undesirable effects to the environment which can be threatening human health, economic, natural resources and gene pool of ecosystems such as pollutions, greenhouse effect, global warming and soil erosion.

Finally, in this paper, we highlights that the environmental protection is worth for fight due to the several reasons and its importance in our Indian society.

Keywords:

Environment, Protection, Environmental Protection.

INTRODUCTION

Environment means all the natural surroundings such as land, air, water, plants, animals, solid material, wastes, sunlight, forests and many other things. Healthy environment maintains the nature's balance as well as it helps in growing, nourishing and developing all the living things on the earth. However, now a days, some man made technological advancement spoiling the environment in many ways which ultimately disturbs the balance or equilibrium of nature. We are keeping our lives in danger as well as existence of life in future on this planet.

In recent passing years mankind's consciousness has been aroused very strongly about the need for environmental protection and ecological preservation. It is of utmost importance that the people should be aware not only of the problems involved but also of the role to be played in protecting the environment. The components of the natural environment are used as a resource however it is also exploited by the human being in order to fulfill some basic physical needs and purpose of life. We should not challenge our natural resources and stop putting so much pollution or waste to the environment. We should value our natural resources and use them by staying under the natural discipline.

HUMAN SOURCES OF ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION

Humans and their activities are a major source of environmental degradation –

Water and Air Pollution

Water and air pollution are unfortunately the common causes of environmental degradation. Pollution introduces contaminants into the environment that can kill plant and animal species.

Urban Development

According to many noted ecologists, including those at Cornell University, urban development is one of the primary causes of environmental degradation. As populations increased, so did the need for land for homes and farms. Wetlands were drained. Prairies were plowed over.

Environmental degradation is one of most urgent of environmental issues. Depending upon the damage, some environments may never recover. The plants and animals that inhabited these places will be lost forever. In order to reduce any future impacts, city planners, industry, and resource managers must consider the long term effects of development on the environment. With sound planning, future environmental degradation can be prevented.

Natural Causes

While environmental degradation is most commonly associated with the activities of humans, the fact is that environments are also constantly changing over time. With or without the impact of human activities, some ecosystems degrade over time to the point where they cannot support the life that is "meant" to live there. Things like landslides, earthquakes, tsunamis and wildfires can completely decimate local plant and animal communities to the point where they can no longer function. This can either come about through physical destruction via natural disaster, or by the long-term degradation of resources by the introduction of an invasive alien species to a new habitat. Sometimes, the environment cannot keep up with the new species, and degradation can occur.

SOME IMPORTANT ACTION POINTS TO PROTECT OR IMPROVE THE ENVIRONMENT

By now, all of us have realized how important it is to protect the environment for our own survival. The term 'conservation' of environment relates to activities which can provide individual or commercial benefits, but at the same time, prevent excessive use leading to environmental damage. Conservation may be distinguished from preservation, which is considered to be "maintaining of nature as it is, or might have been before the intervention of either human beings or natural forces." We know that natural resources are getting depleted and environmental problems are increasing. It is, therefore, necessary to conserve and protect our environment. Following practices help in protecting our environment which are as follows-

- Reuse carry bags.
- Start a compost heap or use a compost bin. This can be used to recycle waste food and other biodegradable materials.
- Avoid unnecessary or wasteful packaging of products.
- Dispose the waste after separating them into biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste material.
- Plant trees. They will help to absorb excess carbon dioxide.
- Never put any left-over chemicals, used oils down the drain, toilet or dump them on the ground or in water or burn them in the garden. If you do so, it will cause pollution.
- Don't burn any waste, especially plastics, for the smoke may contain polluting gases.
- Use unleaded petrol and alternate sources of energy, and keep the engine properly tuned and serviced and the tyres inflated to the right pressure, so that vehicle runs efficiently.
- Avoid fast starts and sudden braking of automobiles.

- Walk or cycle where it is safe to do so – walking is free; cycling can help to keep you fit.
- Treatment of sewage, so that it does not pollute the rivers and other water bodies.
- Judicious use of fertilizers, intensive cropping, proper drainage and irrigation.
- Rotation of crops.
- Composting organic solid waste for use as manure.
- Harvesting of rain water.
- National parks and conservation forests should be established by the government.
- Planting trees in place of those removed for various purposes.

CONCLUSION

In such busy, crowded and advanced life we must take care of such types of small bad habits on daily basis. It is true that only a small effort by the end of everyone can bring a major positive change towards our declining environment. We should not use the natural resources in wrong ways for just our selfishness and fulfill our destructive wishes. We should grow and develop science and technologies for the betterment of our lives but always be sure that it would not ruin our environment in future in anyways. We should be sure that new technologies would never disturb the ecological balance.

So, it is a major worldwide issue which should be solved by the continuous efforts of everyone. We should participate in the World Environment Day campaign to actively participate in the environment safety event.

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